

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP), 2020 AND YOGA EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF INDIA

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Abstract:

The curricular content at higher level of education in India was heavily loaded with core subjects, professional education and skill components, only to the exclusion of value-based education depicting the glory of Indian knowledge and culture. There was an urgent need to create a value education program that promotes holistic personality development and a healthy lifestyle for the young minds and body that shall also impart essential ancient Indian values and skills in them.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a transformative shift in India's educational framework, emphasizing a holistic and interdisciplinary learning approach. A key aspect of this policy is the acknowledgment and incorporation of 'yoga' into the curricula of Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs), with an objective of internationalizing this ancient Indian knowledge. The core tenet of NEP 2020 is to preserve and enhance the rich heritage of ancient Indian knowledge and practices. In this context, educational institutions in India are encouraged to strategically employ yoga-related courses to promote meaningful social engagement and learning and facilitate value education for the comprehensive (all-inclusive) development of younger generations that shall also unlock their full potential. Additionally, the policy aims to establish an integrative healthcare education system that underscores the importance of yoga alongside Allopathy, Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, and Homeopathy.

This paper analyses the impact of NEP 2020 in facilitating and promoting 'yoga' in the higher educational institutions of India. The author seeks to emphasize how NEP 2020 not only aligns with India's rich cultural heritage but also addresses contemporary health concerns, making it a vital aspect of modern education in the country. It is realized that with the incorporation of 'yoga' in an education policy will assist to aspire the young 'future(s)' of India to inspire a state of bliss, freedom, happiness, and peace in the lives of many.

Keywords: Yoga, National Education Policy, Value-Based Education, Indian Knowledge, Higher Educational Institutions, Personality Development

1. INTRODUCTION

In India, the education system has undergone numerous transformations to meet the evolving needs of its diverse population. The most recent and significant reform in this trajectory is the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, which aims to overhaul the Indian education system, making it more holistic, flexible, multidisciplinary, and aligned with the needs of the 21st century. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, of India aims that the entire education system is to be reconfigured to support and foster learning, so that all of the critical targets and goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development can be achieved.

Among all its salient features, one unique feature of this policy is that the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP) recognizes the valuable heritage of ancient and timeless Indian wisdom and philosophy as a guiding principle. It aims to incorporate Traditional Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) into the curriculum at all levels of education. IKS is defined by its profound connection to India's cultural richness, traditions, value systems, knowledge base, spirituality, and a sense of harmony with nature. This vast field includes diverse areas of knowledge such as Ayurveda, Yoga, Vaastu Shastra, Jyotisha, and traditional Indian arts and crafts. Thus, the NEP seeks to highlight the importance of inculcating the sense of rootedness and pride in India, including its rich, diverse, ancient and modern culture and knowledge systems and traditions – such as Yoga. In Indian philosophy, the quest for knowledge, wisdom, and truth has always been regarded as the ultimate human aspiration. The purpose of education in ancient India extended beyond merely preparing individuals for worldly life or life after schooling; it was aimed at the holistic realization and liberation of the self. Hence, through NEP 2020, the primary objective of curriculum and pedagogy reforms at all educational stages will be to shift the system towards genuine understanding.

Yoga is the single most area of learning, which is capable for effecting total development of human personality. Yoga has its roots in Indian culture and traditions, and it is scientific in method and content like any other academic discipline. In view of the importance accorded in the NEP 2020 to rooting the curricula and pedagogy in the Indian context and in the corpus of Indian Knowledge System, every student enrolled in a UG or PG programme is thereby encouraged to take credit courses in Indian Knowledge System – such as Yoga Education. The NEP 2020 also expects to include naturopathy and the AYUSH (Ayurveda, Yoga & Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, Sowa Rigpa and Homoeopathy) system.

The inter-relationship between yoga education and the National Education Policy (NEP) of India underscores a transformative approach. This integration is designed to cultivate a balanced lifestyle, resilience, and inner harmony among students, preparing them to navigate the complexities of modern life with greater ease and confidence.

Moreover, the NEP's emphasis on experiential learning, critical thinking, and ethical values finds a natural ally in yoga education. Yoga's principles of mindfulness, discipline, and self-awareness resonate with the policy's goal of creating well-rounded individuals who can contribute positively to society.

By embedding yoga into the educational system, the NEP aims to foster an environment that encourages lifelong learning and personal growth, echoing the holistic ethos of ancient Indian educational traditions. This synergy not only honors India's rich cultural heritage but also equips students with the tools necessary for a balanced and fulfilling life, embodying the true spirit of education.

The paper discusses and analyses the impact of NEP 2020 in facilitating and promoting 'yoga' in the higher educational institutions of India.

2. AIM:

To study the implementation and impact of yoga education in higher education institutions in India as per NEP 2020.

2.1 Objectives:

Assess Implementation:

- Evaluate the extent and methods of yoga education adoption in higher education institutions.

Impact Analysis:

- Measure the effects of yoga education on students' well-being and academic engagement.

Identify Challenges:

- Identify barriers to implementing yoga education and suggest practical solutions.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study on the inter-relationship between yoga education and the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 of India is primarily doctrinal.

Doctrinal research, also known as theoretical research, involves the systematic examination and analysis of existing legal doctrines, principles, and frameworks. This methodology is particularly suited for exploring the theoretical underpinnings and policy implications of integrating yoga education within the NEP 2020 framework.

By employing a doctrinal research methodology, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the inter-relationship between yoga education and the NEP 2020.

The doctrinal research approach for this study involves a comprehensive and structured analysis of various primary and secondary sources. Data collection for this doctrinal research involves sourcing information from various documents and publications, including:

(a) Primary sources:

- Official policy documents and reports from the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development and Ministry of AYUSH.

(b) Secondary sources:

- Academic journals, books, and articles on yoga education and educational policy.
- Legal databases for relevant legislation, case law, and judicial interpretations.
- Expert commentaries and critiques of the NEP 2020 from educators, policymakers, and scholars.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Meaning and importance of Yoga in Education

The term 'Yoga' originates from the Sanskrit root "Yuj," which means "to join" (Yujyate anenaiti Yogah). Essentially, yoga signifies a union. Traditionally, this union refers to the merging of the individual self with the universal SELF. It involves expanding one's narrow, egoistic personality into an all-encompassing, eternal, and blissful state of REALITY.

Pātañjala Yoga is one of the six classical systems of Indian philosophy known as Śaḍdarśanas. The sage Patañjali, a revered Seer, compiled the core features and principles of Yoga—previously scattered across Yoga Upaniṣads—into concise aphorisms known as 'Sūtras' about 4000 years ago, according to some noted Western historians. Patañjali defined Yoga as a conscious process of mastering the mind (the Citta).

The Bhagavadgītā and Upaniṣads present a more comprehensive scope of Yoga. Swami Vivekananda describes it as "a means of compressing one's evolution into a single life

or even a few months or hours of bodily existence." Generally, growth occurs through interactions with nature, which can take thousands or millions of years for natural evolution, as seen in animals. However, humans, equipped with discrimination, conscious thought (Buddhi), and developed voluntary control systems, seek to accelerate their growth. Yoga provides a systematic and conscious process to significantly compress this growth.

Sri Aurobindo emphasizes holistic personality development at physical, mental, intellectual, emotional, and spiritual levels. He views Yoga as a methodical effort towards self-perfection by developing the individual's latent potential. This process removes limitations and imperfections, potentially leading to a superhuman race. In summary, Yoga is a systematic process that accelerates an individual's comprehensive growth, allowing them to achieve higher states of consciousness.

Research has shown that yoga practices can significantly improve cognitive functions such as attention, memory, and executive function. In an educational context, these enhancements lead to better academic performance and a greater capacity for learning. By incorporating yoga into the curriculum, schools can help students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for success in the 21st century.

The increasing prevalence of mental health issues among students, such as anxiety and depression, underscores the need for effective interventions within the educational framework. Yoga, with its emphasis on mindfulness and self-awareness, provides a natural and effective means to improve mental health. Regular practice of yoga can reduce stress levels, enhance mood, and promote a sense of inner peace and well-being.

Yoga education also encompasses the teaching of ethical and moral values through the principles of Yamas (ethical disciplines) and Niyamas (personal observances). These principles encourage students to develop qualities such as non-violence, truthfulness, self-discipline, and contentment. Embedding these values in education helps in building character and fostering a sense of social responsibility among students.

Yoga is an inclusive practice that can be adapted to suit individuals of all ages, abilities, and backgrounds. This makes it a valuable tool for promoting inclusivity within the education system. In addition to benefiting students, yoga can also enhance the well-being of teachers. Educators who practice yoga are better equipped to manage stress and maintain a positive, supportive learning environment. This, in turn, positively impacts their teaching effectiveness and the overall classroom atmosphere.

Yoga instills a lifelong habit of self-discipline and self-care, which are essential for continuous personal and professional development. By introducing yoga at an early age, the education system can encourage students to adopt a lifelong commitment to physical

and mental health. This aligns with the NEP 2020's goal of creating a culture of lifelong learning and adaptability.

4.2 Yoga Education in India

The Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) mandates Health and Physical Education, which encompasses Health Education, Physical Education, and Yoga, as compulsory subjects from grades I to XII in its affiliated schools.

The Government has incorporated Yoga training into the 'Study in India' program to attract international Yoga seekers to obtain authentic training in India.

The University Grants Commission (UGC) has approved the establishment of an Inter University Centre for Yogic Science in Bengaluru and introduced Yoga as a subject in the National Eligibility Test (NET) starting January 2017. To further promote Yoga, Yoga Departments have been set up in nine Central Universities.

A Yoga Certification Board (YCB) has been established by the Government to standardize and enhance Yoga training by certifying individuals and accrediting institutions. The AYUSH Ministry's Department for Information Education and Communication (IEC) Scheme carries out various activities, such as TV and radio programs, print media campaigns, seminars, and workshops, to raise public awareness about Yoga.

The Morarji Desai National Institute of Yoga (MDNIY), an autonomous organization under the Ministry of AYUSH, serves as the central institute for planning, training, promoting, and coordinating Yoga education, training, therapy, and research.

Through the 'Skill India' initiative, over 96,196 candidates have been trained as Yoga instructors and trainers across the country under various programs of the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), including Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL), Short Term Training (STT), and Special Projects.

4.3 National Education Policy, 2020 – Vision for 'Yoga' as an IKS

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 integrates yoga into its educational framework, aiming to democratize access to physical education, sports, yoga, and mental health initiatives. Furthermore, NEP 2020 advocates for the inclusion of yoga, naturopathy, and the AYUSH system in healthcare education. Additionally, it promotes the integration of Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) into engineering diploma curricula.

NEP 2020, which superseded the 1986's National Policy on Education, has been enthusiastically embraced by the academic community and is effectively being implemented nationwide in India. The Policy aims for an integrative system of healthcare education curriculum. Undergraduate students in medical programs may have

the option to enroll in a first-year credit course focusing on Indian Systems of Medicine. This course aims to give them a foundational knowledge of Ayurveda, Yoga and Naturopathy, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy (NEP 20.2), which are enduring medical traditions serving the health needs of many people in India. In their second year, students can choose to take a two-semester credit course that delves into the Theory and Practice of a specific Indian System of Medicine, including Yoga.

While drafting the four-year undergraduate programme policy, NEP planned that during the initial three semesters of the four-year undergraduate program, students will engage in a common set of courses. These courses shall include language education in both a regional language and English, as well as Yoga Education (among others). NEP's draft framework highlighted that with 2 credits for the 'Yoga education' coursework, students can be prepared to be strong physically and mentally, while helping them integrate their physical, mental, and spiritual faculties. It shall also provide essential knowledge about one's personality, promoting self-discipline and self-control, and shall teach students how to effectively manage various life situations.

Moreover, the "UGC Guidelines for Incorporating Indian Knowledge in Higher Education Curricula, 2023" stated that, considering the emphasis placed by NEP 2020 on integrating Indian context and the Indian Knowledge System (IKS) like 'Yoga' into our curricula and pedagogy, all students in undergraduate (UG) and postgraduate (PG) programs should be encouraged to take IKS credit courses amounting to at least five percent of their total required credits. Students with a strong interest in IKS may take a larger proportion of their total credits in this field.

Course materials for an IKS course – 'Yoga Education', for instance, should be derived from authentic sources, including source texts, historical accounts, inscriptions, material evidence, and thorough sociological records of current community practices. Efforts should be made to showcase the unique features of Indian Knowledge Traditions, such as their objectives, methodologies, and core concepts, which set them apart from other global knowledge traditions. Where applicable, contemporary applications of Indian Knowledge Traditions should be noted. The medium of instruction for IKS courses can be any approved Indian language, in addition to English and Sanskrit.

The '2023 Guidelines' also points that highlighting practical sessions, including traditional memorization techniques and experiential sessions on subjects like Yoga and Ayurveda, should be included in the curriculum. Curriculum development should be closely aligned with teacher training in yoga and allied IKS.

In another guidelines called the "UGC Guidelines for Promotion of Physical Fitness, Sports, Students' Health, Welfare, Psychological and Emotional Well-Being at Higher Educational Institutions of India, 2023" the Higher Educational Institutions (HEIs) are encouraged to develop comprehensive sports facilities both indoors and outdoors within

their campuses. This includes modern gymnasiums and dedicated yoga centers. It is imperative for HEIs to ensure the efficient operation of these facilities. The Sports Council and departments responsible for Physical Education and Yoga should design programs that promote physical fitness and regularly monitor their implementation.

Our cultural heritage emphasizes holistic physical activities such as yoga, and it is recommended that HEIs introduce all students to a range of yogic practices including forward bends, backward bends, side bends, and spinal twists. Additionally, pranayama and heart-centered meditation should be integrated into student activities.

HEIs are also advised to:

- Organize a variety of indigenous and recreational activities, catering from general to specific interests.
- Promote local and nearby adventure and excursion opportunities.
- Establish Memoranda of Understanding (MOUs) with leading institutions in sports, physical education, and yoga.
- Increase the number of trained professionals in sports coaching, physical education, and yoga.

Furthermore, HEIs should adopt supportive measures rather than punitive actions towards students wherever possible. Programs should be implemented that include the services of qualified psychological counselors and promote overall wellness through yoga and meditation practices.

There has been a noticeable rise in the establishment of Yoga Universities, independent Yoga institutions, and Yoga departments within higher education institutions (HEIs), focusing on traditional Yoga and its practices. Consequently, there is a recognized necessity for an accrediting body to oversee Yoga programs within HEIs in India. This accreditation would serve several purposes:

- Upholding and preserving the authenticity of traditional Yoga, viewed as India's contribution to the world.
- Safeguarding and maintaining the essence of authentic Yoga.
- Facilitating the development of ecosystems across HEIs to scientifically explore various dimensions of Traditional Authentic Yogic Principles, encompassing physical, psycho-social, emotional, and employability aspects.
- Cultivating both artistic and scientific approaches to this vast discipline.
- Globally showcasing the extensive scope of Vedic/Indian Psychology embedded within Traditional Yogic Philosophy.
- Elevating standards in the scientific study of authentic Yoga, thereby promoting its standardized growth and global promotion.

With the NEP 2020 in action, the concerned HEIs can come up with a uniform basic outline of a Yoga Education curriculum that can include educating students upon practical training that will further prepare them to assist clients and deliver yoga therapy under medical supervision. The curriculum can also aim to integrate yoga therapy with diverse medical systems and clinical environments, nurturing highly skilled yoga therapists proficient in both basic sciences and holistic health approaches. Basic medical equipments such as pulmonary function test, PEFr, BP, HR, Hb%, SpO₂, Anthropometric measurements, BMI, BMR, and RMR can be integrated for specialized studies and operation of yoga with modern medicine.

Furthermore, students can be given the knowledge and resources to develop communication and computer skills applicable to the field of yoga science. NEP envisions that HEIs take into account the local and global needs of the country and with a respect for and deference to its rich diversity and culture. India, which was a leader of knowledge in the ancient times, must continue to be the torchbearer and knowledge leader in the coming future.

The National Education Policy 2020 represents a forward-thinking blueprint aimed at revolutionizing India's education framework to be more inclusive, equitable, and prepared for the future. By prioritizing accessibility, quality, and holistic growth, the policy has the capacity to redefine the educational environment and empower the country's young generation.

However, achieving its objectives hinges on collaborative endeavors, innovative approaches, and unwavering dedication from all involved parties. Effective implementation necessitates concerted efforts and sustained engagement from stakeholders across the board.

5. CONCLUSION

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is a transformative blueprint aimed at overhauling India's education system to be more holistic, flexible, and aligned with 21st-century needs. It emphasizes inclusivity, quality, and the integration of traditional Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), particularly yoga education. This paper has explored how NEP 2020's implementation fosters a comprehensive, balanced, and culturally rooted educational experience.

The policy views yoga as a holistic educational tool that enhances cognitive functions, mental health, ethical values, and inclusivity. The integration of yoga into higher education promotes lifelong learning and personal growth, resonating with ancient Indian educational traditions.

The policy's focus on experiential learning, critical thinking, and ethical values aligns with yoga principles, fostering well-rounded individuals capable of positive societal

contributions. By embedding yoga into the educational system, NEP 2020 honors India's cultural heritage and equips students with the tools necessary for a balanced and fulfilling life.

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